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DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING ENHANCEMENT CUM ASSESSMENT SYSTEM FOR THE COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop a Listening Enhancement cum Assessment System for the College of Teacher Education students that responds to their identified listening comprehension needs. The system features were designed based on the students' initial listening comprehension mastery level and refined through expert input. Using descriptive and developmental research designs, data were gathered from sixty student-respondents who were identified through total enumeration sampling. Findings revealed varying levels of listening comprehension mastery among the students, which served as the basis in the development of the Listening Enhancement cum Assessment System. The system integrated interactive listening tasks, automated assessment features, immediate feedback functions, and user-friendly navigation as its primary features. Student-respondents rated the system as highly satisfactory in terms of content and technical quality. Based on the results, the study concludes that the Listening Enhancement System is appropriate, functional, and beneficial for improving the listening comprehension skills of College of Teacher Education students. Continuous use, periodic evaluation, and user feedback are recommended to further enhance the system's effectiveness and sustainability.

KEYWORDS: Listening Comprehension, Educational Technology, Listening Enhancement System, Automated Assessment, Interactive Listening Tasks, Language Learning Development, Teacher Education Students, System Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Successful English language learning requires communicative competence in the different macro-skills such as viewing, listening, speaking, reading and writing. It should also include knowledge of a plethora of activities that help students focus on both meaning and accuracy. Prior to the proficiency of the other language skills, listening plays an active role to enhance them.

In this study, it focuses on listening skills as one of the essentials in learning English as a second language. For several decades, listening is considered as an important facet of language learning; however, Rassul (2024) claimed that listening was given lesser attention among the five macro skills and it is almost ignored in both primary and secondary level where students spent more than ten years in English language learning. Further, In the ESL classroom, learners and teachers face different challenges and problems regarding listening (Sumalinog, 2019). Therefore, the need of innovative instructional materials is needed which are essential in enhancing the listening skills of the learners especially during this present time where face to face modality sometimes shifted into hybrid modality. These could further help learners in enhancing other competencies and innovate an assessment tool which can be utilized by learners. Teachers do not just simply use it as an instructional material in developing learners' skills but also as an assessment tool.

Moreover, Philippines ranked 20th out of 100th in the world's largest ranking of countries and regions in the EF English Proficiency Index (EF EPI). English Proficiency Index (EF EPI) is based on a test data from more than 2,300,000 test takers around the world who took the EF Standard English Test (EF SET) (Philstar Global, 2020). Key stakeholders from the government, academe, private, and non-government sectors acknowledged that though the Philippines is competitive in the English language, the concern is on how much of a competitive advantage the country is.

Finally, studies prove that the development and utilization of technology-aided materials is one way to address learners' needs and enhance students' second language competencies (Hsueh, 2014). It gives L2 learners opportunities to get large amounts of L2 input and provides an efficient medium with which such skills like listening can be trained and enhanced (Gu et al., 2018). Enthused by the mentioned concepts and studies, this study fills the gap on the development of the listening cum assessment system that enhances listening skill. It is

hoped that this study contributes to the dearth of listening system not only in the local context but also globally that can be mutually helpful to teachers and students in improving listening skill.

1.1. Objective of the Study

This study aims to develop a listening enhancement cum assessment system. Specifically, it aims to determine the listening comprehension mastery level of the College of Teacher Education students, the features of the developed listening enhancement system, and the level of satisfaction of the College of Teacher Education students on the listening enhancement cum assessment system in terms of content and technical quality.

2. METHOD

2.1. Design

The study utilized the descriptive and developmental research design. Descriptive research design makes use of a normative survey which is used to collect demographic data about people's behavior, practices, intentions, beliefs, attitudes, opinions, judgments, interests, and the like and then such data were analyzed, organized and interpreted (Koh & Owen, 2000). Moreover, developmental research is defined as the systematic study of designing, developing and evaluating instructional programs, processes and products that must meet criteria of internal consistency and effectiveness (Shambaugh, 2007). This study described the learners' listening comprehension mastery level. It is the basis in the development of listening enhancement cum assessment system which was evaluated by the respondents in terms of its technical and content qualities.

2.2. Procedures

This study was conducted at Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College Santa Maria Campus. There was a total of 60 CTE students who were enrolled during the 1st semester, school year 2024-2025 who served as respondents of the study. They took up BSEd-English. Total- enumeration sampling was used in this study. Prior to the conduct of the study, ethical considerations were considered. Consent forms were given to the respondents. After approval, the researcher gathered the needed data for the study. Listening comprehension test was administered to the respondents at their most convenient time. Moreover, the researcher consulted a programmer who created the codes appropriate for the design of the listening enhancement cum assessment system made by the researcher. Its

features were then identified. After the development of the system, questionnaires were also distributed to the respondents about the satisfaction of the respondents. Finally, the gathered data were tallied, treated, and it were subjected for analysis. Participation in this study was handled with the utmost confidentiality and ethical consideration. Respondents were fully informed about the study's purpose, their role, and their rights, and their consent were obtained prior to participation. Data were anonymized to protect the identities of the respondents. In this study, permission was sought from the author of the selected questionnaire to use and adapt it for the specific context of listening enhancement. Proper citation and acknowledgment were done. Ethical guidelines were strictly followed to ensure the integrity and trustworthiness of the research process and findings.

2.2.1. Instruments

This study utilized questionnaire to gather the needed data for the study. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. Part 1 is an adopted listening comprehension test from the (International English Language Testing System) IELTS (2024) with a total number of 20 items which was given to the respondents to test their listening comprehension mastery level. Part 2 was used to measure both content and technical quality of the system based on the level of satisfaction of the respondents. This was adopted from the evaluation models created by Turel and Mkkena (2015).

2.2.2. Data Analysis Method

Mean was used to determine the listening comprehension competencies mastery level and the satisfaction level of the respondents in the listening comprehension cum assessment system.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Listening Comprehension Mastery Level of the Respondents

The mastery level of the listening comprehension competencies of the learners was identified through the raw scores that they obtained during the test (Table 1). Each student answered the test using the developed system. Among the nine listening comprehension competencies, it is evident from the table that the competency with the highest percentage, analyze the content of utterances and make prediction or a stand based on the text or statement of the speaker, was mastered by 58% of the learners. This means that the learners after listening

to a piece of material can make a stand or a decision for them based on the content of a speech they heard. This competency is mastered by the learners because it is also taught in the lower year level of English classes. As the learners move into higher level of education, they took similar listening comprehension competency at different levels. Mukhamedova (2025) emphasizes on the language teaching principle of spiral progression skills where grammatical items, structures and various types of texts are taught, revised and revisited at increasing levels of difficulty and sophistication. This allows learners to progress from the foundational level to higher levels. In this case, making a stand based on a listened text is a basic skill.

Table 1: Learners' Mastery Level in Listening Comprehension Competencies.

Mastery Level of Learners in Listening Comprehension Competencies	Percentage of Students Who Answered the Items Correctly	Descriptive Rating
1. Judge the relevance and truthfulness of the ideas listened to	37	Least Mastered
2. Listen to paraphrase and summarize information from the text listened to.	39	Least Mastered
3. React and share opinion about the ideas listened to.	28	Least Mastered
4. Compare and contrast information listened to	18	Not Mastered at All
5. Reflect or Interpret on the ideas of the speaker listened to	16	Not Mastered at All
6. Get the different sides of social, moral, and economic issues affecting the nation	51	Somewhat Mastered
7. Process information mentioned in the text listened to	13	Not Mastered at All
8. Analyze the content of utterances and make prediction or a stand based on the text or statement of the speaker listened to	58	Mastered
9. Draw generalizations and conclusions from the material listened to	55	Somewhat Mastered

3.2. Features of the Developed Listening Enhancement System

Parts of the System The parts of the system include the log-in page, dashboard, and menu.

The log-in page The log-in page is where the user, either the learner or the teacher opens the listening enhancement system using his or her own Gmail address and a password (Figure 2). Password should be private and it can be made using special characters like signs, numbers and letters. The login

page allows a user to gain access to an application or site by entering their username and password or by authenticating using a social media account. There are two possible results when a user log-in. It could be the authentication is successful and the user is directed to the application landing page. On the other way around, authentication fails and the user remains on the login page. If authentication fails, the screen should show an informational or error message about the failure (Marchioni, 2020).

Figure 1: The Log-in Page.

To register in the system, the teacher inputs basic information like complete name, email address, password, number, country, city, and address. If the teacher and learner log-in, they can manipulate and control everything presents in the system. Through registration, it means that a user is ensured to the benefits available to the system.

Dashboard The dashboard presents all possible transactions that the user, either the teacher or learner can manage and control. It includes learners' dashboard and teachers' dashboard. The dashboard organizes and presents information in a way that is easy to read. It may include collection of graphical elements. Also, it may provide data visualizations or a control panel from which to accomplish multiple actions (Rouse, 2020).

i. Teachers' dashboard. The teacher controls this part of the system because s/he organizes all the listening comprehension tasks for learners. He adds, edits, and deletes all the information namely learners' profile, listening comprehension competencies, questions, audios, and students' scores in the teachers' dashboard. Once scores are recorded, the teacher can also delete answer sheets of students. When listening comprehension tasks are added and made by the teacher every week, learners can access it through the learners' dashboard during the schedule for listening activity. The teacher enhances and tracks the learners' listening comprehension competencies through updating and checking the dashboard (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Teachers' Dashboard.

Conveying information to the users through the dashboard makes the easiest and effective access of a system. Users only need to embrace the capabilities of dashboards (Rao, 2019).

ii. Learners' dashboard. The learner's dashboard is where the learner sees all the things that he or she can manage or control in the system (Figure 4). All the listening comprehension competencies are present with its corresponding questions and audios and it is already organized for the learners to do the comprehension tasks. In addition, this is also the part where the learner can automatically view the answers once comprehension task is done. Lastly, the profile of the learner can also be viewed and edited.

Figure 3: Student's Dashboard.

Menu Menu is a set of options presented to the teacher and learner to help them find information and execute program functions related to listening comprehension competencies. It includes the teacher's menu and learner's menu. This offers commands to the users. By accessing it, features of the system appear. It could be found either on the upper right or left corner of the screen depending on the design of the system (Norman, 2010)

i. Teacher's menu. The teacher's menu contains the students' profile; listening comprehension competencies, questions included for listening comprehension tasks, audios, and students' scores (Figure 5). The teacher adds or edits learners' profile for them to be included in the list of users who can

access the learners' dashboard where listening comprehension tasks are taken.

Figure 4: Teacher's Menu.

Additionally, listening comprehension competencies can also be added and edited depending upon the listening comprehension competencies of grade nine learners. Audios serve as springboard or oral text which the teacher uses. It can be made by the teacher or it can also be downloaded from any source of audios. The audios are uploaded in the system. Moreover, questions and choices could also be placed by the teacher in the system, either adopted or made. Lastly, the option for all the learners' report can be seen in order for the teacher to track learners' progress in listening comprehension competencies.

ii. Learner's menu. This menu comprises information which can be accessed and controlled by the learner in enhancing his listening comprehension competencies. It includes reports, test and profile (Figure 6). All the listening

Figure 5: Learner's Menu.

Comprehension tasks made by the teacher in the

teacher's menu will appear here and it will be taken by the learner through taking the option take test. Once done, he can automatically see his scores. He can also review answers on my reports option. His profile can also be edited and manipulated in the menu.

Procedure

Teacher's procedure. When listening comprehension tasks are added and made by the teacher every week in the listening enhancement system, learners can access it through the learners' dashboard (Figure 7). The teacher enhances and tracks the learners' listening comprehension competencies through updating and checking the dashboard once s/he logs-in using gmail address and a password. If not yet registered, he may register by creating an account through entering required information in the system like name, gmail address, password, number, and address. Once the teacher already has an access to the system, teacher's dashboard appears, everything can be manipulated by the teacher through adding, editing, and deleting information. In the dashboard, options like total students, total quiz, total questions and delete all answer sheets also appear. The teacher can also click the arrow for more information about the options. He may also view the latest updates on the students' information. Through the procedure, it provides a guide for meeting the objectives of the material and describes the overall steps that users are to take when engaging to a specific task. This ensures consistency in practice and helps to maintain quality response to the system. Performance is identified if the process was followed appropriately (Lutich, 2020). Finally, in order to create the learners' listening comprehension tasks, the user can manipulate the following menus:

i. Competencies. In this part of the system, the teacher could input, edit and delete the listening comprehension competencies. Upon clicking competencies in the system, the teacher can simply input the particular listening comprehension competencies through clicking add. In addition, the teacher can decide how many points (click per question mark) and how much time (click test time) he will give on a listening comprehension task when the learner takes it. Since the system automatically checks and records scores after the learner takes the comprehension task, the teacher has also an option if he wants or not to let him see the answers (click enable show answer). Lastly, description of each competency may or may not also be added by the teacher through clicking description.

Figure 6: Teacher's Procedure.

ii. Questions. Upon clicking the menu for questions, all the listening comprehension competencies appear with its corresponding descriptions, points per item, total number of questions, total marks and total time that the learners need in taking the listening comprehension task. Questions are therefore interconnected with a specific audio/ springboard and listening comprehension competency. The teacher either adds questions (click add question) on a particular listening comprehension competency or deletes all the answer sheets (click delete answer sheets) of the learners when they already took and recorded the test. When the teacher decides to add questions, it can be either constructed or adopted depending on the needed listening comprehension competency. To add necessary information in this menu, the teacher clicks question, options for question, correct answer, and answer explanation. The teacher can edit the question for the oral input that is needed in determining and enhancing the listening comprehension competencies of the learners. Correct answer can also be an input so the system can automatically check the answers of the learners. Answer explanation can also be another input in order to justify the answers once the teacher decides to do so. Available options for adding a video or image can also be accessed by the teacher when he desires to make use of it as a springboard through either clicking add video or add image to the question.

iii. Audios. Audios can be uploaded in the system which is used as an oral input or springboard for enhancing the listening comprehension competencies of the learners. The title of the audio can be the first input (click audio name). The teacher may upload any type of audio either customized or downloaded (click choose file). The chosen audio can

come from any storage device. It is then connected with a specific listening comprehension competency. Description of audio can also be an input if the teacher desires either to put it or not (click description). Once audios are present in the system, actions like edit and delete audio may also be done by the teacher (click either delete or edit).

iv. Student report. The teacher can click the option, student report, after it, listening comprehension competencies appear first together with the information of each competency like point per question, total marks, and total time in taking the test. Show Report option shows the list of the learners with the total items that they answered. Since the system can automatically check the answers of the learners, either right or wrong, all answers and total scores appear. The arrangement is not in a chronological order. Top student report menu is similar with student report menu; the only difference is that the results or scores of learners in comprehension tasks is presented in a descending order. This helps the teacher tracks the learner in his listening comprehension competencies.

Learner's procedure. If registered by the teacher, the learner needs to log- in using his gmail address and password to access the listening comprehension competencies tasks (Figure 8). If not, he needs to create an account to access the system (click create account). Information like name, email address, mobile number, city, address, of the learner is the entries. If the learner already opens the system, he can already view the dashboard and menus. He can access already all the listening comprehension tasks prepared by the teacher from the teacher's dashboard. Different listening comprehension competencies appear. The learner needs to do the listening comprehension task through clicking one among the listening comprehension competencies (click take test). Then, audio and first question appear. Guided by the teacher, the learner can play the audio twice only since there is an allotted time to take the test in each listening comprehension task. The learner needs to answer first question before proceeding to the next question. In answering questions, the learner may answer either orally or through choosing one among the options. If he is finished answering the first question and wants to proceed on the next listening comprehension competency, he simply needs to click next. After answering all the questions in each competency, the learner can automatically see the results with complete details on right and wrong answers. To proceed in the next listening comprehension competency, learner needs to click the arrow beside

his name, then click dashboard, followed by take test. All the listening comprehension tasks will again appear. Learner may proceed on the next listening comprehension competency to complete all the comprehension tasks. Once the learner finishes all the comprehension tasks, he can view all the results through clicking my reports. On the teacher's dashboard, the results of the comprehension tasks will also appear. This will enable the teacher monitor the learner's progress if learner is done in the comprehension tasks.

Figure 7: Learner's Procedure.

3.3. Level of Satisfaction of the Learners on the Listening Enhancement cum Assessment System in Terms of Content and Technical Quality

Content Overall, learners' evaluation of the listening enhancement system in terms of content is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.55. This means that in terms of content of the listening enhancement system, it has provided the learners with enough information appropriate to their level and needs.

In details, specific items with descending order of means are also described as very satisfactory. The first item has the highest mean of 4.73 specifically "gives tasks anchored to listening comprehension competencies". This means that all the tasks included in the listening enhancement system focus on the development of the listening comprehension competencies of the learners. This is through enabling the learners to be exposed in different learning materials and activities. In each of the materials and activities, the learners have to answer questions repetitively until they are able to master the content of the materials. In addition, listening to the material and doing the assessment expose the learners to the tone of the language which sharpens their listening skills. Alisoy (2022) emphasized that listening awakens awareness of the language as it is

a receptive skill that first develops in a human being. Learning to listen to the target language improves language ability, competence and comprehension.

The criterion, "includes proper type of language that I can understand and contains comprehension tasks related to language and learning" with a mean of 4.73 is described as very satisfactory. It means that the learners understood the language used in the system. It uses English that exposes learners with the language features of the native speakers. Listening comprehension tasks are also present in the system that encourages learners not only to learn but also to familiarize themselves with the English language. As Nugroho et al. (2020) said that it has been well established that sufficient and suitable language input is a vital component of language learning.

Another criterion, "offers task that enhances my listening comprehension competencies" has a mean of 4.70 described also as very satisfactory. This means that comprehension tasks present in the system are in line with the listening comprehension competencies. The tasks of listening to audios are coupled with objectives to be attained and the system allows the learners to use different strategies that are of help to accomplish the task objectives. Gilakjani (2020) emphasized that listening comprehension is an important part of language learning which can be exercise through exposure to various task types.

The criterion, "relates tasks applicable to real world situations" with 4.64 mean is evaluated as very satisfactory. The listening enhancement system presents real-life situations that are found in the listening tasks. It makes the learners understand better the information present in each topic. Through the system, they could relate their experiences while accomplishing each task. It further gives them interest to listen with the audio and construct new learning from it. Liubiniene (2009) mentioned that the goal of listening instruction is to equip learners with the skills to comprehend texts that are related to real life situations.

Similarly, with the same mean of 4.73, "contains comprehension tasks related to language and learning" is described as very satisfactory. This is because the system provides authentic tasks that also expose the learners to the use of the English language. Through the tasks, learners become familiar with the spoken language and features speech. Their listening skills are sharpened as they are used to the intonation, pronunciation and accent. Liubiniene (2009) emphasized that language is best learnt through exposure to large amounts of interesting, enjoyable, comprehensible texts.

Table 2: Learners' Evaluation of Listening Enhancement System.

Criteria	Mean	Descriptive Rating
offers task that enhances my listening comprehension competencies	4.70	Very Satisfactory
provides me task that has clear communicative goals	4.55	Very Satisfactory
gives tasks anchored to listening comprehension competencies	4.73	Very Satisfactory
relates tasks applicable to real world situations	4.64	Very Satisfactory
contains comprehension tasks related to language and learning	4.73	Very Satisfactory
encourages me to engage on listening activities	4.58	Very Satisfactory
stimulates me to use bottom-up or top-down processing skills includes input of my interest	4.39	Very Satisfactory
encourages me to use different listening strategies	4.27	Very Satisfactory
motivates me to respond	4.48	Very Satisfactory
includes proper type of language that I can understand	4.73	Very Satisfactory
gives me task that is structured and can be undertaken at different levels of difficulty	4.58	Very Satisfactory
offers a range of macro skills integrated into the sequence of tasks	4.58	Very Satisfactory
provides me with mastery of the linguistic system	4.39	Very Satisfactory
incorporate task that exercises learning-how-to-learn	4.39	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.55	Very Satisfactory

Moreover, the item, "encourages me to engage on listening activities" has a mean of 4.27 described as very satisfactory. It means that the comprehension tasks in the listening enhancement system are captivating that they arouse the interest of the learners. It provides the learner audios and questions that are challenging and that giving up doing the activities was never an option for the learners. This very positive response of the students allows them to reach the lesson objectives set Mcinerney & Liem (2008) emphasized that learners who are motivated by and engaged in learning tend to perform considerably higher academically and are better behaved than unmotivated and unengaged peers.

In the criterion, "offers a range of macro skills integrated into the sequence of tasks", the system is rated as very satisfactory. The system gives the users experience to use also the other macro skills since these are integrated with listening. Though more focused on listening comprehension tasks, it enables learners to monitor their progress or level they are in. The system can give learners listening comprehension tasks that enable them also to

respond in an alternative way like speaking. As Liubiniene (2009) reiterates, learners have expressed a strong desire to improve their listening skills and the lessons cannot consist of listening instruction alone, as other skills will need to be developed.

On the criterion, "gives me task that is structured and can be undertaken at different levels of difficulty", it has a mean of 4.58 described as very satisfactory. This means that the tasks were organized in a way that it ranges from simple to complex. In this manner the students can have the options to choose the level of difficulty he will have to work on. This brings positive effect on the learners' effort in understanding the input. It requires them to make use of their skills and effort in accomplishing the task. Qodir (2016) emphasized that listening is a good source of comprehensible input where listening materials may present things that are already known plus some which have yet been mastered by the learners.

Moreover, the criterion, "provides me task that has clear communicative goals" has a mean of 4.55 described also as very satisfactory. The listening enhancement system provides listening comprehension tasks with objectives that are to be attained by the learners. All the listening activities are geared towards achieving a particular purpose. As an example, one of the communicative goals as stated by Pesce (2020) is to help learners understand native English speakers, not only for the mere purpose of comprehension, but also so they may respond accordingly and interact with others. In the system, these types of goals are clearly stated to guide the learners on what to do with the activities.

Another item in the evaluation instruments that is very satisfactory is "the task motivates me to respond". Learners were interested to engage in the listening comprehension tasks provided in the system because of the authentic and experience-based nature of the activities. This makes the learners eager to do more the comprehension tasks and to listen more to the audios. As Husnawati et al. (2024) states, when designing lessons and teaching materials to further develop listening comprehension skills, students need to be motivated and stay motivated by hooking them into liking the materials.

Further, the item, "the material stimulates me to use bottom-up or top-down processing skills" has a rating of very satisfactory. Bottom-up processing enables learners to utilize details present in the listening enhancement system. It enables them decode the meaning of the information present in the system. Top-down processing lets the learners with what they already know in the information that they

received from the system in order to understand it. Both processing is used because listening has a complex process. As Liubinienė (2009) further emphasized, listening is a complex multistep procedure that involves different types of processing which are both top-down and bottom-up skills. This should be practiced in the classroom. In addition, Rukthong & Brunfaut (2020) emphasized two different processes to be used when listening to an oral text and trying to understand it: bottom-up processes and top-down processes.

The criterion "includes input of my interest" is also rated as very satisfactory. In the listening system, the tasks given to learners are different topics for the input that caught their attention. Since learners are heterogeneous, the listening comprehension tasks topics also vary. The tasks were specially designed according to the learners' background and interest. Khaldi (2017) strongly posits that it is crucial for learners to have access to quality and quantity input that they need for effective learning unless it is in line with their interest.

Similarly, the item, "provides me with mastery of the linguistic system" is also described as very satisfactory. It means that learners realized that their exposure to the several listening tasks allows them to be exposed too to the native English language. Their listening skills in terms of sound recognition are enhanced that they can already identify correct and appropriate pronunciation, accent etc. Renukadevi (2014) emphasized that to understand the nuances in a particular language, one must be able to listen. As learners get to understand spoken language by listening, it is easier to improve the skill and gain confidence.

Incorporate tasks that provide exercises on learning-how-to-learn is another criterion that was rated as very satisfactory. Learners were able to enhance how to do things with the use of the system. It also lets the learners work independently through the use of the listening enhancement system. Also the tasks allow learners to think about learning and how they are learning while doing the listening tasks. This allows the learners assess the task if there's other possible way to achieve understanding of the information present in the material. Renukadevi (2014) added that one's own learning can be controlled especially when it comes to listening comprehension. Other than being the primary form of communication, listening helps the language learner to understand the beauty of the language.

Further, the criterion encourages me to use different listening strategies motivates me to respond has a mean of 4.27 described as very satisfactory. This

means that the listening enhancement system consists of varied listening comprehension tasks. When learners access the system, it challenges them to use different ways of understanding the input. They listened with different purposes. In looking at the content, the learners select and connect the strategies for effective listening. Ross (2006) opines that ineffective listeners rely on a single strategy without changing or adapting it. Learners need to cope with difficult texts more effectively, and students should be exposed to a variety of strategies.

Generally, this means that learners reached the highest level of satisfaction in the listening enhancement system. Learners are equipped with knowledge and skills in manipulating digitized learning materials that could enhance various skills in English language learning. This is affirmed by Borsheim et al. (2008) as they said that the integration and proliferation of technology and rising consciousness on cultural diversity and globalization have shifted the traditional notion of learning to 21st century learning. Learners collect and/or retrieve information, organize and manage information, evaluate the relevance, quality, and usefulness of information, and generate accurate information through the use of available resources (Educational Testing Service, 2007). These are the skills that contemporary learners must possess to survive today's highly globalized economy (PPRC, 2010 as cited by Barrot, 2018). The Partnership for 21st Century learning (2015) includes principles of 21st century teaching and learning which mastery of core subjects is. The 21st century themes include creativity, critical thinking, and communication and collaboration which are important in preparing learners. Learners must be able to display a range of functional and critical thinking skills related to information, media, and technology to be effective 21st century citizens and workers. They must be able to develop adequate life and career skills to thrive in this globally competitive information age, curriculum should adopt 21st century standards that focus on 21st century skills, content knowledge and expertise, developing deep understanding, building understanding across subjects, engaging learners with real-world data, tools and experts, and allowing multiple measures of mastery. Notably, the LAMC/K to 12 was developed to address the needs of the Generation Z (those born from 1994 to 2004) and to equip them with various literacies that will help them thrive in this global and knowledge-based society. As cited by Kevin (2011), (Alliance for Childhood, 2010), the use of digital technologies should be emphasized in the learners' experiences and the value of such

experiences for their physical, cognitive and socio-emotional development.

Technical Quality Overall, the learners' evaluation of the system is described as very satisfactory with a mean of 4.46 (Table 8). This implies that learners could use the listening enhancement system without any interference. If problems occurred, public support is available anytime so it can be addressed automatically. The highest mean of 4.63 includes the item, "the system performs properly when I used it" (overall

performance). This means that the system was responsive during use and was able to function based on the desired command of the user. The system provided the learners with the correct feedback when that command option was chosen. It properly executed the commands in the menu as accessed by the learners. This gives the good quality of the system. As Fish (2008) emphasized, a "just works" software also has good usability and it behaves like people expect it to establish conventions rather than creating proprietary or counter-intuitive ones.

Table 3: Learners' Evaluation on the Software in Terms of Technical Quality.

Criteria	Mean	Descriptive Rating
The site can easily be accessible once I log- in. (Ease of Access)	4.25	Very Satisfactory
The sounds are audible and the texts are readable. (Hardware Compatibility)	4.12	Satisfactory
The system can be accessed using my device. Ex. Windows, OS, Android etc. (Operating System Compatibility)	4.43	Very Satisfactory
The options present in the system can be managed and controlled. (Consistency with Interface)	4.49	Very Satisfactory
The system is complete and organized in its presentation. (Completeness and Organization of Documentation)	4.57	Very Satisfactory
The system uses a language that is clear and understood. (Clarity of Documentation)	4.52	Very Satisfactory
A contact support is readily available when I encountered related issue or problem. (Accessibility of Product Support)	4.18	Satisfactory
A quality support is available when I encountered related issue or problem. (Quality of Product Support)	4.55	Very Satisfactory
The system did not fail in its functions. (Overall Reliability)	4.60	Very Satisfactory
The system performs properly when I used it. (Overall Performance)	4.63	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	4.46	Very Satisfactory

The next criterion in the evaluation is "the system did not fail in its functions" (overall reliability). It is evaluated as very satisfactory. This means that the functions of the system for teacher and learner work out very well. From the log-in part, dashboard, and menu, the procedure was followed and it did not fail in its purpose. All the options present in the system automatically open once the learner chose it. As Kharagpur (2020) reiterates that reliability of software product essentially denotes its trustworthiness or dependability. Alternatively, reliability of a software product can also be defined as the probability of the product working "correctly" over a given period of time.

Also, other items are described by the learners as very satisfactory with a descending order of means. First, "the system is complete and organized in its presentation" (completeness and organization of documentation) which has a mean of 4.57 is described as very satisfactory. In the system, the

content is properly arranged. It has complete parts which make the teacher and learner can manipulate properly. These parts are visibly clear in each dashboard. This also allows them to explore every part of the system with easiness. Kittlaus and Clough (2009) mentioned that well-structured software is like enabling the users to roam around in a strategic manner helping them find their way.

Further, another item, "A contact support is readily available when I encountered related issue or problem" (quality of product support) has a descriptive rating of very satisfactory. This means that the system has a ready backup. This helps in a situation when problem arises. The support of the system could help fix the problems once it occurs. This ensures the usability of the material to the learners and teachers. During the use of the system, the learners did not encounter any technical problem. There was a smooth flow in the use of the system. However, any time, a product support is available.

Elice (2020) emphasized that having a backup of system can help in many situations. If a learner loses crucial data or gets hacked, having a backup readily available can solve problems. Plus, it often doesn't take more than a few minutes to get that backup file ready.

The criterion, "the system uses a language that is clear and understood" (clarity of documentation) was rated very satisfactory. The system was accessed by the learners with readable content. This was made possible through its organized content and correct use of language. It allowed the learners to easily take any information present in the system and helps them avoid misinterpretation. It made them to the right direction and chooses the right option when accessing the system. Through this, learners were able to understand the content. Antunes and Lopes, (2019) mentioned that readability is one of the most important aspects of software. Readable texts affect how users process the information in the content. Poor readability scares readers away from the content. On the other hand, done correctly, readability allows users to efficiently read and take in the information in the text. It makes users to be able to read content and absorb it easily.

Moreover, the item, "the options present in the system can be managed and controlled" (consistency with interface) has a mean of 4.49 described as very satisfactory. This means that whatever option is chosen by the learner in the system, he can easily open it. The system allows the users to navigate or move around the system at their own pace. Also, consistent positions of the parts of the system avoid confusions and continue the access the system with good interface. De la Riva (2018) mentioned that the importance of consistency in software design has a good reason. User interfaces that are not consistent often yield to confused and frustrated users and can drive even the most promising software's to failure.

For the item, "the site can easily be accessible once I log- in" (Ease of Access), it has a mean of 4.25 described also as very satisfactory. This means that the system lets the learners easily use and access it. This could be by means of using their gmail ad and password. Rosenzweig (2025) said that software should not only look good but also provide a seamless user experience for visitors.

Further, the item, "the system can be accessed using my device. Ex. Windows, OS, Android etc." (Operating system compatibility) has a mean of 4.43 described as very satisfactory. This means that the system can be accessed whether with computer units. Aside from the personal computer, cellphones could also be used to open it. Devices which are android for

Microsoft Windows accepts the system. The system works well with the external means of navigation present in the device like the keyboard and screen. Dorsey (2017) said that a device compatible with software is an HTML (Hyper Text Manual Language) based that is standard which enables responsive design and cross platform compatibility.

On the other hand, "a quality support is available when related issue or problem (accessibility of product support) has a mean of 4.18 described as very satisfactory. If problem arises, the learners can easily contact a support who can fix the problem in the system. This can be done anytime. This also helps the users maintain the function of the system. It includes seeking for the updated version of the material. This also helps in the continuous use of the system. Without the support, systems or any material won't be useful after problem arises in it. Neuvo (2017) said that the role of a technical support is to provide assistance and maintenance to all computer systems and hardware. It may include installing, configuring, and updating hardware and software, as well as fixing any issue related to the equipment that may come up on a daily basis.

Lastly, on the item, "the sounds are audible and the texts are readable" (Hardware Compatibility) has the lowest mean of 4.12 described as "satisfactory". This means that the system allows the learners to access the system in different devices which makes them use the earphone, monitor and mouse. These provide them alternative ways of accessing the system. Henry (2019) said that accessibility encompasses all disabilities that affect access to the material, including auditory and visual.

Overall, it only implies that the student-respondents have positive feedback in the usage of the software. Though, attention on enhancing the product support and hardware compatibility is needed, the system meets the satisfaction and needs of the learners. Koko (2016) confirms that the main purpose of using materials in teaching and learning is to concretize students' learning and achieve set goals of education. Materials bring about desired behavioural changes of the learners while evaluation helps to build an educational program, assess its achievements and improve upon its effectiveness. It serves as an in-built monitor to review the progress in learning from time to time. It also provides valuable feedback on the design and the implementation. Through it, forming the values of judgment, educational status, or achievement of learners is formed. On the other hand, Kervin et al. (2011) added that technology offers the possibility of using powerful cognitive tools that students can use

to solve complex and authentic problems. For this to happen, however, the technology must be used in a theoretically sound manner, and it must be the students who use it rather than the teachers. Moreover, Tomlinsom (2012) emphasized that the characteristics of the software should be considered for the improvement and for tailoring superior outcomes. Also, Kakar (2012) mentioned, in order to have the overall performance, there should be functionality which deals to the degree of performance of the software against its intended purpose and reliability that refers to the ability of the software to provide desired functionality under the given conditions. He added, other characteristics like usability: extent to which the software can be used with ease, efficiency: the ability of the software to use system resources in the most effective and efficient manner, maintainability: ease with which the modifications can be made in a software system to extend its functionality, improve its performance, or correct errors, portability: ease with which software developers can transfer software from one platform to another, without (or with minimum) changes. In simple terms, it refers to the ability of software to function properly on different hardware and software platforms without making any changes in

it. In any computer related application, usability and maintainability are key factors to be considered (Sparrow, 2020). As Thakur (2020) emphasized, in systems where human life is at stake, integrity and reliability factors must be given prime importance. Thus, the listening enhancement system functions properly and it meets its purpose.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of the study reveal that respondents demonstrate varying levels of mastery in listening competencies, indicating the need for targeted instructional support. The development of a listening enhancement system was found to be beneficial in improving learners' mastery of the prescribed listening competencies, providing structured and accessible learning opportunities. Furthermore, students' evaluation of the system in terms of content and technical quality confirms that the material is appropriate, functional, and responsive to the needs of its users. Overall, the results highlight the importance of integrating well-designed technological tools to support and strengthen students' listening skills development.

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